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Crack Damage Detection and Size Assessment in CFRP Plate Based on Magneto-Strictive Transducer

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) plates are gradually replacing steel in the aerospace and automotive sectors due to their high specific gravity and strength. In service, the material is assembled in the form of a shell riveted or bolted to the selected substrate to ensure that the material is firmly connected to the surface. In this paper, we present detection of hole-cracks phenomenon by using low-frequency ultrasonic guided wave to monitor the health state of CFRP plate structure. The excellent magneto-strictive (transducer) coupling characteristics of Galfenol material and the dispersion equations for Lamb and SH0 wave were solved by using COMSOL software. The ultrasonic transducer was designed for excitation of low-frequency guided wave. Thus, convected wave equation simulation and experiment verified that super transducer and stimulate the Lamb wave (S0), mode wave (A0), feasibility wave (SH0). Then, based on the magnetic circuit Ohm's law and the driving magnetic field required by Galfenol, the sizes of each component and the relevant parameters have been designed. In order to improve the propagation energy of Lamb wave in the crack damage detection, an optimization convected wave method is used for defect determination. Simulation results show that the particle displacement in CFRP plate is increased by 65.3% after optimization, which proves the effectiveness of the proposed convected wave method. Using ultrasonic guided wave and mechanical magneto-strictive technology to monitor the structure strength of the hole, the position and degree of damage can be obtained effectively. Lastly, the experiments were completed which determined that the defect position was critical and improved. The coordinate error is controlled fewer than 11.09%.

Keywords

Magneto-strictive transducer, carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) plates, numerical simulation, galfenol material, convected wave method

Introduction

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) is a material consisting of several constituents: a base or carrier substance, known as the matrix, and a second, reinforcing material embedded in the matrix. For the latter, fabrication process uses carbon fibers or glass fibers, depending on the application [S.H. Cho et al 2006]. The result: high-performance materials with exceptional properties, which a company can tailor individually to suit requirements. Composites materials made from CFRP that have superior material properties in comparison with metallic components i.e., light weight, robustness, damage tolerance, fatigue strength and corrosion resistance [B. Yoo et al 2014]. Moreover, several CFRP are manufactured by mixing carbon fibers and plastic resin under recommended conditions. These materials are distinguished by their high strength and rigidity, low density, excellent damping properties [Y.M. Wang et al 2006]. Moreover, due to high resistances to impacting and corrosion combining with modifiable thermal expansion to complement complex characteristics profile it is implemented in many surfaces. Further, because of their excellent mechanical properties, CFRP materials have been widely used for critical components and structures, such as aircraft fuselage and wing structures, helicopter rotors and windmill blades, road and marine vehicle body structures, and, bridges and large civil infrastructures [H. Nishino et al 2010]. However, CFRP also has some unavoidable shortcomings and technical problems. Because the transition shears strength and tensile strength of composite laminates do not match the shear and tensile strength of the matrix. Therefore, the transition cracks damage is easy to occur during mechanical processing and service progression. Due to the presence of residual strength, stiffness and the useful life will significantly decrease cracks; seriously affect the reliability and safety of the structure [L. Du et al 2009].

Composite materials have the characteristics of good corrosion resistance, excellent specific gravity and high strength, which are widely used in industrial fields. The demand for CFRP in the aerospace industry is greater than ever. As a mass production services, they can provide benefit from their wide range of materials and expertise across all processing stages from fibers to the final lightweight structure. By using CFRP in both primary and secondary structures, it is possible to save weight and at the same time achieve mechanical peak values in terms of strength and stiffness of the components [S.K. Lee et al 1997]. With innovative production technologies and years of experience in the manufacture of lightweight components, CFRP offer tailor-made solutions due to its significant demand and requirements. In high-tech applications requiring high strength and stiffness combined with light weight, therefore CFRP components are indispensable. The properties of CFRP materials bring to bear precisely when other materials reach their limits. CFRP is considerably lighter than aluminum or steel, while being extremely durable [L. Laguerre et al 2002].

In the aviation field, CFRP material has the advantages of high strength and high temperature resistance to resist the impact of high-speed airflow and airflow. Frictional heat has led to an increasing proportion of CFRP materials used in the aerospace industry. Such as the Asian Airbus A380 passenger and the aircraft uses carbon fiber composite materials up to 30 tons, accounting for about 13% of the total weight of the structure [K. Xu et al 2014]. In the wind blade generator, carbon fiber composite material reduces the

weight of a wind turbine blade which is gradually reduced, the rigidity of the blade is improved and further the power generation efficiency of the wind turbine is greatly increased [M. Rucka et al 2010].

Until now, many scholars at their home countries and abroad have paid attention to develop this crucial problem. Similarly, micro-cracks in metallic plates by nonlinear wave propagation [A. Sellitto et al 2020] were detected by Jingpin et al. Similarly, Zuo et al. presented a novel model-based 2D multiple signal classification damage identification algorithms for different plate structures [S. Mustapha et al 2016]. Jie Wen et al. conducted an experimental study on the damage detection of carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites via electrical resistance measurement. The study determined that this self-sensing NDE method can be used to detect various damages such as fiber breaks, matrix crack and delamination in CFRP materials under various loading conditions such as tensile loading, bending and cyclic loading [J. Wen et al 2011]. Xu Liang et al. accompanied an experimental study on the behavior of laminate turn composite with delamination damage under clean shear conditions. Further, the team obtained the results by analyzing the deployed test throughout the process. Hence, the degree of delamination damage has a significant effect on the bearing capacity of the composite laminate [L. Du et al 2009]. Abdeslam Aoukili et al. demonstrated a simulation and experimental work on the damage detection of cracks in carbon fiber reinforced composites by pulsed eddy-current testing. Similarly, considering a B-scan strategy which consists in moving a probe along a straight path, the FE modeling under COMSOL multi-physics software packages was performed in this work. A probe compound by two coils: inductive and receiver is analyzed under TEC excitation. The objective was to study delectability of a small defect through monitoring impedance changes of detection probe [A. Aoukili et al 2018]. Beata Zima et al. reported the detection and size estimation of crack in plate based on guided wave propagation. However, the study had shown that the amplitude value could be also influenced by the interaction with the damage. The meaningful differences in the amplitudes of waves reflected from various damage zones (the end and middle point) had become the foundation of the novel algorithm of line-crack detection. Yi Mei Qi et al. used cohesive force model and also used progressive damage analysis to study the residual compressive strength of typical structures, and discusses the sensitivity of residual strength to various factors [B. Zima et al 2020]. He Shuai et al. calculated the buckling characteristics of pre buried laminated plates under compression load, and conferred the effects of different shapes of layers (circular, elliptical, rectangular), size and location on the bearing capacity of laminated plates [S. He et al 2017].Pereira G.F et al. presented crack detection in fibre reinforced plastic structures using embedded fiber-bragg grating sensors. The theory and model development was validated in experimental study. They demonstrated detailed study of damage mechanism (delamination of FRP), the structural health monitoring technology (fiber Bragg gratings to detect delamination), and the finite element method model of the structure. Similarly, all the concepts were described and incorporated into a final and integrated damage-monitoring concept in entire study [G.F. Pereira et al 2015]. According to the suggested literature, the hole-crack damage detection and optimization on CFRP are still challenging using the convected wave method due to the unfavourable properties of composite materials. Thus, such composite materials should explore optimization for the industrial application.

In this paper, the main objective is to detect and measure the health state of different holes in the crack of the CFRP plate to check the stability of materials. Convected wave detection method was found to reduce the interference of the ultrasonic wave signal directed by multi-mode CFRP plate. Moreover, the signal characteristics are collected under different degrees of cracks to observe the rapid and instinctive reaction of the process, in order to realize the qualitative problem of the degree of crack damage. In view of the high attenuation coefficient of the acoustic signal of the CFRP plate based on the giant magneto-strictive material, Galfenol alloy and a magneto-strictive transducer. The effectiveness of the proposed method is verified by doing many experiments. The focus of the work is the detection of crack defects and measures the size of holes in CFRP plates.

Simulation and methodology

Materials and setup

The experimental installation used in existing study is based on convected wave detection method, which consists of a magneto-strictive-transducer, carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) plates and galfenol material. The performance parameters of CFRP plate is given in Table. 1. Galfenol alloy has a body-centered cubic structure and exhibits orthogonal anisotropy. The deformation and magnetic saturation of the material after magnetization are related to the excitation direction of the applied magnetic field. Galfenol's main constituent elements are iron and gallium, and its magneto-strictive performance is more than 10 times that of traditional materials [G.F. Pereira et al 2015]. The material adds gallium element to the original ferromagnetic material, which reduces the magnetic saturation intensity and increases the Curie temperature of the material. The specific parameters of the material are shown in Table 2.

Table 1 Performance parameters of CFRP plate

E_1/GPa	E_2/GPa	E_3/GPa	ν_1	ν_2	ν_3	G_{12}/GPa	G_{13}/GPa	G_{23}/GPa	$\rho/\text{kg.m}^{-3}$
165	13	13	0.3	0.3	0.03	3.6	7.1	7.1	1570

Table 2 Performance parameters of Galfenol materials

Performance parameters	Parameters value
Magneto-striction strain rate/ $\times 10^{-6}$	300~400
Tensile strength/MPa	500
Elastic Modulus/GPa	60
Relative permeability	60~100
Magnetic field (Drive conditions)	100oe
Curie temperature/ $^{\circ}\text{C}$	500
Frequency bandwidth	0~1MHz

Simulation analysis of CFRP plate and magnetostrictive transducer

In order to understand the model of a designed transducer and CFRP plate in the xyz medium, the stress simulation of the transducer is carried out, and the strain output of the transducer is theoretically analyzed. The software environment for this simulation analysis is used COMSOL. In order to simplify the simulation model, the modeling environment used is a two-dimensional axisymmetric space. The simulated objects include the output of transducers and elastic waves, including electromagnetic effects, magneto-extensive effects, elastic mechanics and other theories. The physical field is magnetic field and solid mechanics.

We model the joint transducer and CFRP plate according to the structure of the transducer, and the specific construction method is shown in Fig 1. The main components of the known transducer are permanent magnets, magnetostrictive material matrix, and coils. Among them, the CFRP plate material has no available holes options in the material library of the software, so set a blank hole with a radius of each 0.08 mm. According to the original design transducer size, the material width is defined as 1 mm and the length is defined as 2.5 mm. the CFRP plate width and length is defined 10 mm and 4 mm respectively. The magnetostrictive material and the CFRP plate need to be coupled, so the two structures are set as a joint structure to ensure that the strain of the transducer is transmitted into the CFRP plate structure. The joint transducer and CFRP plate model is shown in Fig 1a. Similarly, Fig. 1b illustrates the local refined meshing of the designed geometry. The geometric model dimensions simulated in this paper are mainly based on commercial CFRP plates. In order to reduce the amount of calculation, improve simulation efficiency And accuracy, the simulation model has been simplified in the following aspects:

- (1) Converting a two-dimensional model into a two-dimensional axisymmetric model;
- (2) Ignore the outer diameter of the CFRP plate and holes radius.

The reason for this is that the CFRP plate shape is axisymmetric, and the two-dimensional axisymmetric model is sufficient to express the convected wave equation simulation model. Moreover, the simulation difficulty and calculation amount can be greatly simplified, and the outer diameter of the CFRP plate has no influence on the transducer field. Furthermore, P (1-4) represents the different piezoelectric sensors on CFRP plate and the crack damage is done in center of CFRP plate to check rapid and accurate location of impact damage.

Figure 1. (a) The construction of structural model of CFRP plate using piezoelectric sensors and magnetostrictive transducer (b) The local refined mesh

Convected wave equation method

The convected wave equations method adds the equations for modeling the propagation of acoustic waves in a stationary background flow and check characteristics of various ultrasonic lamb wave (S_0). Adiabatic behavior is assumed, meaning that this in some sense represents pressure acoustics in the presence of flow frequency. The convected wave equation model solves the linearized Euler equations also referred to as linear acoustic equations for moving media. The equations are valid for any stationary background mean flow frequency as long as there are not too large gradients in the background properties. We discussed the approximations of magneto-strictive transducer theory and showed that if the unsteady flow frequency is linearized about the mean lamb wave, and the mean time-frequency perturbations are small. Then the sound radiation from a lamb wave in an unsteady flow can be reduced to the boundary value problem in which the perturbation potential satisfies the convected wave equation and the lamb wave is modeled by a flat plate of zero thickness. The boundary conditions and properties of meshing are shorten during this study due particular specification of convected wave equations. The convective wave equation method is low cost, easier to handle, and less time consuming to use. The main advantage is that using this method the frequency signal analysis during this technique is very realistic.

Convected wave equation simulation

The algorithm decomposes the convected wave into components of different scales according to the continuous low wave frequency. Each component can be processed with different algorithms. For example, in wave cancellation, each component is processed by an adaptive filter with a different filter length to improve convergence. The important problem of this algorithm is to retain all relevant information so that the user can restore the original signal. This algorithm is based on the frequency decomposition relationship of wavelet. For the signal decomposition process, suppose the original signal is decomposed into multiple nested sequences as given in Eq. (1-3).

$$x_{S+1}(t) \in A_{S+1}, \Rightarrow x_{S+1}(t) = \sum_k a_{k,S+1} \phi_{k,S+1}(t) \quad (1)$$

$$x_s(t) \in A_s, \Rightarrow x_s(t) = \sum_k a_{k,s} \phi_{k,s}(t) \quad (2)$$

$$y_s(t) \in W_s, \Rightarrow y_s(t) = \sum_k w_{k,s} \psi_{k,s}(t) \quad (3)$$

The characteristic frequency decomposition process is given in Eq. (4).

$$A_{S+1} = A_s + W_s \quad (4)$$

$$x_{S+1}(t) = x_s(t) + y_s(t) \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_k a_{k,s+1} \phi_{k,s+1}(t) = \sum_k a_{k,s} \phi_{k,s}(t) + \sum_k a_{k,s} \psi_{k,s}(t) \quad (6)$$

Substituting the decomposition relationship, the above formula becomes as given in Eq. (5 & 6).

$$\phi(2^{s+1}t - \ell) = \sum_k \{h_0[2k - \ell] \phi(2^s - k) + h_1[2k - \ell] \psi(2^s t - k)\} \quad (7)$$

Exchange the order of summation and compare the coefficients of $\phi_{k,s}(t)$ and $\psi_{k,s}(t)$ on both sides of Eq. (7) to get Eq. (8 & 9).

$$a_{k,s} = \sum_{\ell} h_0[2k - \ell] a_{\ell,s+1} \quad (8)$$

$$w_{k,s} = \sum_{\ell} h_1[2k - \ell] a_{\ell,s+1} \quad (9)$$

2.1. Low frequency guided waves

The ultrasonic lamb wave (S_0) in the time domain adopts a 5-period sinusoidal modulation signal, which has good concentration in the time-frequency domain and forms a ridge in the mode wave (A_0) transform cloud map. Thus, the unpredicted source of environmental impact noise signal has a certain peak but is not concentrated, it is irregular multiple continuous pulses, under the Fourier transform of the selected window function, the ridge cannot be formed, and it forms irregularities in the time-frequency domain. Therefore, the color threshold adjustment method is adopted to reduce the influence of the low-amplitude noise signal in the mode wave (A_0) cloud chart on the real signal. The collected signal to be processed can be set as:

$$S(t) = S_0(t) + \Delta S_0(t) \quad (10)$$

$S_0(t)$ is the real lamb wave signal, and $\Delta S_0(t)$ is the noise signal. In the high-energy excitation signal, the amplitude of the noise signals $\Delta S_0(t)$ is quite different from that of the excitation signal. Increasing the zero point value of the cloud image threshold can effectively filter low-amplitude noise signals, but an excessively high threshold zero point will filter out the low energy in the CFRP board. In order to optimize the mode wave (A_0) cloud image threshold, the characteristics of the noise signal are calculated and extracted to realize the determination of the threshold range. The experiment collects 100 groups of non-excitation signals and sets them as unpredicted environmental influence noise signals. The point value of each group of signals is the amplitude characteristic of the noise signal. The average calculation formula is as follows.

$$X = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |A_{0i}| \quad (11)$$

Furthermore, it can be seen that the amplitude of the feasibility wave (SH_0) is greater than the calibrated value of the noise signal, so it is possible to reduce the influence of the environmental noise signal without filtering the reflected signal. The calculation formula for the lower bound value range of feasibility wave (SH_0) is as follows.

$$H_0 S = \frac{X}{S}, H_2 = \frac{HS_1}{S}, X < S_1$$

$$k_1 \in (k \cdot H_1, k \cdot H_2)$$
(12)

Results and discussion

Experimental platform

Fig. 3 illustrates a diagram of the experimental equipment. The test board is a square CFRP board with a thickness of 20mm and a side length of 500mm. The fiber layering method is maintaining an angle of 0°/90°. The signal generator model (Tektronix AFG1022), the excitation signal (5-period sine modulation wave), amplified by the signal amplifier (Aigtxk ATA-2021H), and the output voltage peak (180V) are used in this study. Magnetostrictive transducers can generate high-energy ultrasonic signals, but as a sensor, the sensitivity is inferior to that of piezoelectric materials. The sensor uses PZT-5 square patches, which is conducive to collecting the complex characteristics of guided wave signals in the composite board. The sensor is connected to a 4-channel oscilloscope of Tektronix MDO4104C.

Sweep frequency analysis of energy conversion

The color threshold processing result after the short-time Fourier transform of the numerically collected signal is shown in Fig. 3. According to the dispersion curve of the Lamb wave of the CFRP plate, it can be seen that the S_0 mode propagates the fastest, so the first wave packet in the time domain in Fig. 2(c) is the S_0 mode. At the excitation frequency of 70kHz, only S_0 and A_0 modes exist and the propagation speed of S_0 mode is more than three times that of A_0 mode. There are only S_0 mode and reflection S_0 mode information in the limited time domain signal. Further, according to the positional relationship of the detection elements in Fig. 2(a), it can be seen that the path of the hole boundary reflection is the shortest reflection path compared to other boundaries, so the second characteristic SH_0 mode reached in the cloud map is the hole reflection S_0 mode. Under the influence of the 2mm crack, the energy distribution of the reflected wave packet from the original signal hole in Fig. 2(b) becomes longer and there is a corresponding change in the amplitude. It can be seen from the length of the time domain that the time domain area of the S_0 mode of the hole reflection in the signal increases from 7 μ s to 14 μ s. It can be inferred that this is due to a new mode generated under the influence of the crack, accompanied by the hole reflection S_0 mode. The influence of the crack on the signal time-frequency distribution can be clearly seen in Fig. 2(d).

Figure 2. Collect the Fourier transform of the signal (a) STFT of defective signal (b) Short-time Fourier transform of defective signal (c) Hole reflection S_0 mode (c) Without modulation defective signal

Acquisition of ultrasonic guided wave signal of CFRP board

For the detection of CFRP plate hole crack damage at different angles, the experiment shown in Fig. 4 is carried out. A magnetostrictive transducer is used to excite a 5-period modulated sine wave ultrasonic wave of 70kHz in a non-damaged composite plate. A piezoelectric is set at a distance of 250mm in the 0° direction. The transducer receives the signal; under the original experimental conditions, a circular hole with a diameter of 20mm is drilled at a distance of 88mm in the 45° direction as a connecting hole. Repeat the above experimental program to process the cracked CFRP board with a length of $0, 45^\circ 90^\circ$, and 180° on the direction of edge of the hole. Signal Acquisition. Fig. 4 shows the signal acquisition for different degree of crack damaged and undamaged features. It can be observed from the figure that each group of collected signals is accompanied by high-amplitude crosstalk signals after the start of the time domain. Compared with the signal without crack damage, the original signal of the crack damage signal is attenuated and deformed and a new modal wave packet is generated in the area of concentrated amplitude. The collected signal contains a variety of modal information, which makes it difficult to observe the characteristics of defects.

Figure 3. (a) Diagram of experimental equipment (b) CFRP Plate containing holes

Figure 3. Signal acquisition for different degree of crack damaged and undamaged

The method with significant modal can capture the crack damage. After the analysis of influence of the crack signal, the damage degree of crack is further analyzed, and then the use of proposed signal processing method for damage detection is explored.

Quantitative analysis on crack damage of CFRP plate

Compared with Fig. 5(b) to Fig. 5(a), the modal 1 distribution has not changed greatly and only a small change in the energy amplitude. It can be preliminarily inferred that the damage degree of the crack has an influence on the signal modal distribution and amplitude, but it cannot be quantified. For this reason, the signal is further Fourier transformed and the frequency domain is analyzed to realize the defect quantitative problem.

Figure 6 is the dispersion curve of different guided wave mode at the wave angle of 0° and 45° respectively. The frequency domain diagram of the crack damage signals at 45° is superior to check identify damaged surface of CFRP plate accordingly A0, S0, A1, S1, A2 and S2 etc. It can be seen from the figure that the amplitude quantity of S0 at the center frequency of 70 kHz is larger than that of the A0 in Fig. 6(a). In the frequency band near the center frequency, its peak distribution has not changed. It can be seen that the damage degree of the crack affects the amplitude of the center frequency signal, so the amplitude can be extracted from this frequency and the damage degree can be deduced by comparing with the original damage signal. However, when the CFRP material is damaged, the center frequency amplitude of its frequency domain is suddenly reduced, and then its frequency amplitude slowly rises as the crack grows. Therefore, it is impossible to use the Fourier transform under the condition of no damage. Moreover, even if the effect of damage on the original signal can be observed from the figure, the effect of crack length and other modal effects are difficult to identify.

Figure 4. Signal color threshold value to process STFT (a) Collection signal of 4mm crack damage (b) Acquisition signal of 2mm crack damage

Figure 5. The dispersion curve of different guided wave mode (a) at the wave angle 0° (a) at the wave angle 45°

In order to realize the quantitative problem of different degrees of crack damage and understand influence of the degree of crack on signal amplitude distribution in frequency domain. We analyze the extract regional amplitude exceeding time domain of A0 reflection due to S0 mode and the SH_0 mode as illustrated in Fig. 6(b). The bandwidth of guided wave discussed the damaged features of hole reflection.

The modal peaks and amplitude results comparison is shown in Fig. 7. The black shading in the figure shows that the S0 mode is affected by different crack damage conditions and its amplitude gradually decreases after being affected by the damage. The reflection mode of the corresponding fringe shading also decreases in amplitude as the crack grows. The corresponding red shading is the crack-affected amplitude area produced by SH_0 and red shading amplitudes affected by the 2mm, 4mm, and 6mm cracks in the extraction are 0.00130, 0.00133, and 0.00141, respectively. It can be judged that as the crack grows, the modal energy scattered by the original signal by the defect gradually increases. Therefore, from the STFT cloud image (A0) after color gamut processing, the effect of defects can be found and the crack can be quantified by extracting the amplitude of the influencing mode wave packet that are represented in blue color. However, the amplitude changes of the S0 mode and hole reflection mode cannot be explained from figure, so the signal propagation path is analyzed and characterization of collected signal is further explored.

Figure 6. Extraction of modal peaks of Lamb waves from crack damage

Conclusion

This paper proposes an applicable method for crack damage detection of CFRP materials that is the convected wave processing method to improve the signal modal resolution in the amplitude and frequency domain to view defects and then judge the damage degree by the modal peak value. The research and proposal of this method is an exploration in the field of non-destructive testing of composite materials. More, a magnetostrictive transducer is designed to realize high-frequency excitation of ultrasonic waves, which can detect composite materials. It is an attempt to detect magnetostrictive transducers under high-frequency signal detection conditions. This work conducts theoretical and simulation research on laminated materials of composite materials and performs simulation calculations on them. Acoustic characteristics and dispersion characteristics of materials are obtained by signals. The analysis results are helpful to the study of material characteristics. Furthermore, according to the simulation calculation and analysis of the excitation wave of the designed new giant magnetostrictive transducer, it can be seen that the excitation waveform of the transducer has transverse wave, longitudinal wave and horizontal shear wave, and the excitation guided wave signal has the SH_0 mode. Comparing the frequency sweep experiment of the transducer and the peak value extraction of the S_0 mode, it is determined that the optimal excitation frequency of the S_0 mode of the transducer is 350 kHz, which is a good result of the experiment as an excitation transducer. The convected wave processing and STFT methods greatly reduce the influence of noise signals and unpredicted noise cannot be ruled out. The multiple modal wave packets of the Lamb wave signal collected in the CFRP board are seriously aliased and the signal analysis is difficult. The S_0 mode and the propagation time of hole reflection S_0 calculated by theoretical velocity and the experimental prediction error are $3.2\mu s$ and $0.7\mu s$, which are in good agreement with the actual value.

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